

IMPLEMENTATION OF MECHANISMS FOR DEVELOPING CLINICAL THINKING COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS OF HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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*As the President of the Republic
of Uzbekistan Shavkat
Mirziyoyev noted*

ABSTRACT

Educational processes are being consistently reformed in order to train highly qualified and competitive personnel for the healthcare system of our country. In recent years, our republic has been creating a regulatory framework for the development of science in medicine, identifying priority areas of scientific research, improving medical culture, and ensuring the harmony of medicine and science. Rapid reforms, scientific education, and innovative activities have a positive impact on the development of society.

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As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "Our people should know this well: we have a long and arduous path ahead. If we all unite, study tirelessly, do our work perfectly and efficiently, acquire modern knowledge, and strive forward without sparing ourselves, our lives and society will certainly change." This requires the development of medical culture in higher medical education institutions, that is, the creation of an environment of clinical thinking, the methodological improvement of pedagogical activities, the development of technologies for organizing the educational process, as well as the formation of a system of competencies related to science and activity and the further improvement of their mechanisms.

In medical education, real-life case analysis, simulation exercises, and group discussions play a special role as modern methodological approaches to deepening students' knowledge, forming clinical thinking, and developing professional decision-making skills. These approaches bring the learning process closer to real practice from artificial conditions, transforming the student from a passive learner into an active participant and problem-solving professional. Real-life case analysis is a method of analyzing a complex case that reflects clinical reality. In this approach, the student learns to make a complete diagnostic judgment by linking the patient's symptoms, laboratory and instrumental examination results, medical history, social background, and psychological factors. Case analysis is not just about memorizing facts, but also about thinking, coming to conclusions, and making informed decisions. Each student's decision is discussed, different points of view are compared, and medical decisions are developed based on consistent reasoning. This process creates conditions close to real life and prepares the student for the professional environment.

Simulation training serves as an important platform for avoiding errors in medical practice. They are organized on the basis of staged situations with the participation of special mannequins, robotic patients, virtual programs or actors. Simulation allows the student to make quick decisions in a complex clinical situation, correctly plan the sequence of diagnostic and therapeutic actions, maintain team coordination and test communication skills. In such training, along with medical knowledge, competencies such as psychological stability, stress management, teamwork and reflexive analysis are developed. The student practices in a clinical environment without the risk of making mistakes, which allows him to consolidate knowledge not only in theory, but also in practice. Analytical discussions - "debriefings" held after simulation training are the most powerful developmental stage of the learning process. In this process, the student reconsiders his actions, analyzes his mistakes, evaluates alternative options and reflexively studies his professional decisions.

Group discussions are one of the main forms of interactive methods, developing the skills of exchanging ideas, reasoning, critical analysis and developing alternative approaches among students. During a group discussion, each participant justifies his or her position, listens to the views of others, and reconsiders his or her decisions. This method teaches students to communicate professionally, express opinions politely, and engage in healthy criticism and self-evaluation. Especially in a multidisciplinary approach, when students from different fields analyze a situation together, comprehensively illuminated complex decisions are made. Through the process of collective thinking, students feel clinical responsibility not only at the individual but also at the team level.

In medical education, clinical thinking can be deepened by combining interactive methods, problem-based learning, clinical simulations, virtual case modeling, hypnopaedia, and collaborative learning methods. Such modern teaching methods develop students' competencies in independent thinking, professional reflection, development of alternative solutions, and teamwork.

Interactive methods such as simulation training, clinical case studies, and OSKE, which are widely used in practice, not only strengthen students' theoretical knowledge, but also prepare them for real clinical practice. For example, with the help of simulation training, students practice providing emergency care in various emergency situations; in the case study method, clinical situations are analyzed step by step and alternative diagnostic solutions are developed.

Interactive educational technologies form the principle of "student-centeredness" in students. Based on this principle, the student acquires knowledge not in a ready-made form, but through his active search, discussion and decisions. The teacher appears as a process manager, a guide to clinical situations and a scientific and methodological assistant. The role of interactive educational methods in medical education is that they are one of the most effective pedagogical mechanisms for combining theoretical knowledge and practical skills in future doctors, forming clinical competencies and achieving professional maturity.

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